

Challenges Faced by Geography Teachers: Implications on Students' Academic Performance in Meme Division of the South West Region of Cameroon

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates Challenges faced by Geography Teachers and their Impact on Students' Academic Performance. Data were obtained through the use of questionnaires and interviews. The target population of this study consisted of 147 Geography teachers, 120 students and 12 principals. The sample was limited to 12 selected secondary schools (4 Public, 4 Confessional and 4 Lay private) in Meme Division. The sampling techniques employed were the purposive, the convenience and the simple random sampling. Data were essentially of categorical variables and they were analyzed using frequency and proportions and Multiple Response Analysis for grounding of concepts that merged from open-ended questions. Reliability test was performed to assess the internal consistency of responses using Cronbach Alpha reliability analysis. Chi-square test was used to compare proportions for significant difference. Relationships between conceptual components were assessed using Parametric Pearson's correlation test. Data were presented using frequency tables, charts, code-grounding-quotation tables and conceptual diagram. The data analyzed yielded the following responses: challenges faced by Geography teachers in relation to teaching aids had a significant impact on students' academic performance in Geography (the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted). Challenges faced by Geography teachers in relation to classroom management had no impact on students' academic performance in Geography (the null hypothesis was accepted and the alternative hypothesis was rejected). Challenges faced by Geography teachers in relation to

teacher/student/administrator relationship had a positive impact on students' academic performance though not significant (the null hypothesis was accepted while the alternative hypothesis was rejected). Challenges faced by Geography teachers in relation to implementation of the syllabus had a significant positive impact on students' academic performance in Geography (the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted). Challenges faced by Geography teachers in relation to teachers' working conditions had no impact on students' academic performance in Geography (the null hypothesis was accepted while the alternative hypothesis was rejected). At the end of this study, recommendations were made to policy makers, proprietors of schools, teachers, students and parents towards improving students' academic performance in Geography. Finally, suggestions for further research were pointed out.

Keywords: Challenges, Geography Teachers, Students' Academic Performance, Meme Division of South West Region of Cameroon

INTRODUCTION

As much as all occupations face challenges or problems, the teachers are not left out of this scenario. As such, the challenges of teachers deserve attention in order to resolve classroom conflicts which will lead to increase students' academic performance. Research on the challenges of teachers is therefore critical in order to bring about a positive change in students' academic performance. It is against this that this study seeks to investigate the challenges or problems

teachers' face in teaching and how they can be solved in order to achieve educational goal or success. Therefore, the following questions were raised; what are the problems they encounter? What are their proposals for the way forward?

Background to the study

Cameroon has a national system of education based on the following orientation: acknowledgment that education constitutes a major mission as stated in the preamble of the Constitution of 16th, January 1996. The provision of quality education to every child is guaranteed by the state (Report of the Technical Committee for the Elaboration of a Sector-wide Approach to Education, 2005). The long term vision of this country is to ensure that it is:

powerful, sovereign, a catalyst of economic and social progress and have qualified and motivated human resources and be united in diversity in which unity and integration are visible in the respect of differences and identity-ies. Values such as the respect of authority, cohesion, solidarity, integrity, work and pride will be watchwords for individual and collective behaviors. (Cameroon, Growth and Employment Strategy Paper, 2010-2020, p. 53)

The report does not only present the challenges but goes ahead to make proposals for the way forward, among them the development of its human resources. More specifically, "to provide the nation's human resources with the skills necessary for building an emerging Cameroonian economy by 2035" (p.76) In relation to the education sector, the Growth and Employment Strategy Paper (GESP) reforms are designed to improve access, equity, and quality; forge more efficient partnership with the various stakeholders, and strengthen governance and management. Part responsibility for the successful implementation of actions aimed at achieving the GESP vision and goals lies with the education sector because it can be referred to as 'the mother of all the sectors'.

Quality education requires effective teaching, consequently the quality and role of the teacher becomes paramount. One of the critical challenges of the education sector in the Republic of Cameroon is to ensure that teachers are of the best possible quality. To do this requires paying attention to their recruitment, training, induction and continuing

professional development. It also requires paying regular attention to their conditions of service. It is important to pay attention to the quality of teachers because they are critical to the effectiveness of the education sector. They have been referred to by the Law of Orientation for Basic, Secondary and Teachers Education of April 14, 1998, as the 'guarantors' of the quality of education. Consequently, ensuring the smooth transition of teachers from colleges of education or wherever they are prepared to assume teaching responsibilities to the world of practice requires deliberately planned and implemented actions. The teachers' attention is required by stakeholders, parents, the community and the students in particular.

Education which can be said to be the process of imparting knowledge, skills and attitudes to younger generations is more than just what takes place in schools. Education takes place in varied ways and different locations over time; sometimes without notice (Mbua, 2003). Before the white man came to Cameroon, this country like other African countries educated their people following their traditional and cultural norms. This system of education is often called indigenous education because it emanated from the people themselves (Shu, 1985). It was also called primitive education by the Europeans because according to them, it was not well developed with a specific curriculum, formal structures and written down.

The philosophy that provided indigenous education was education for preservation, earning a livelihood, raising children, and participating fully in the society. Here, various skills were taught to the young in different fields such as hunting, farming, traditional music, craftsmanship, traditional medicines etc. The main method of education was learning on the job (Shu, 1985). This provided direct employment for nearly everybody in the Cameroonian traditional society. According to Shu (1985), indigenous education cemented the virtues of communal living which was typical of most African societies at that time. Formal education began in Cameroon in 1884 by the English Baptist Missionary Society along the coastal regions (Mac Ojong, 2008); (Tambo, 2003) and (Shu, 1985). The Cameroonian school system evolved through independence and reunification in 1961 into the present day post-colonial era, with French and English being the official languages used as a medium for instruction. The growth and

expansion of secondary education in Cameroon began in 1939 with the creation of the first secondary school (St. Joseph's College Sasse in Buea). This has resulted to the proliferation or establishment of many secondary schools. One of the aspects that have led to the success of these schools is how teachers manage their classes.

Classroom management is widely viewed by most educators, as the number one concern in schools. From 1967 through 1997 results of researches identified classroom management as the most important problem that teachers face (Jackson, 2005). Some researchers ranked classroom management as the second greatest problem facing schools (Jackson, 2005). Many teachers lack training in the use of effective classroom management strategies. Researchers (Hoy, 1990; Marzano, 2003; Schmidt, 1992) found that classroom managerial problems can have a substantive impact on the effectiveness of teaching and quality of learning. Classroom management is a term used by teachers to describe the process of ensuring that classroom lessons run smoothly despite disruptive behaviour by students. The term also implies the prevention of disruptive behaviour. It is possibly the most difficult aspect of teaching for many teachers; indeed experiencing problems in this area causes some to leave teaching altogether. In 1981 the US National Educational Association reported that 36% of teachers said they would probably not go into teaching if they had to decide again. A major reason was "negative student attitudes and discipline" According to Moskowitz & Hayman (1976), once a teacher loses control of their classroom, it becomes increasingly more difficult for them to regain that control. Also, research from Berliner (1988) and Brophy & Good (1986) shows that the time a teacher has to take to correct misbehaviour caused by poor classroom management skills results in a lower rate of academic engagement in the classroom. From the student's perspective, effective classroom management involves clear communication of behavioural and academic expectations as well as a cooperative learning environment.

In 1995, Cameroon through its Ministry of National Education, organized a national forum aimed at taking stock of basic, secondary, and teacher education and to make necessary recommendations for improvement. This forum according to Tambo (2000) was the largest education gathering after

independence, comprising Cameroonians from all walks of life with their foreign partners to discuss issues affecting the Cameroon educational system. According to the forum's documents (MINEDUC, 1995), the following reasons necessitated the holding of the forum: the poor implementation (or the non-implementation at all) of the legislation dealing with education, as well as certain provisions necessary for promoting bilingualism; excessive centralization with regard to the administrative, pedagogic and financial management of schools; poor management of resources (for example, teachers) placed at the disposal of the then Ministry of National Education (MINEDUC), and too many unqualified teachers.

One of the key challenges identified by the 2005 Sector-wide Education Conference was the improvement of the quality of educational services across various levels of schooling. The call for improvement of the quality of educational services has brought about new challenges for principals and teachers of secondary schools in Cameroon. In addition, education in Cameroon is considered as the nerve Centre of the entire national life. Section two of Law No. 98/004 of April 14 1998 to lay down guidelines for education in Cameroon stated that "education shall be the top priority of the nation" and that "it shall be provided by the state" as well as partners from the private sector. The law further identified teachers as the guarantors of quality education while emphasizing the fact that the provision of quality education is a shared responsibility among all members of what it described as the "education community". In order for teachers to guarantee the quality of education, their conditions of service need to be improved. This is particular so in the case of new teachers who are likely to be concerned about issues of self-doubt. The difficulties they face as beginners can be addressed by other teachers and schools as organizations.

Cameroon functions within the context of an international community, and is signatory to a number of international conventions and a member of the United Nations Organization, the African Union, among others and must therefore respect its international and regional obligations, especially those related to strengthening teacher quality. One of the key obligations has to do with educational commitments such as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted by the United Nations General

Assembly in 1948, with basic education being one of these rights. This declaration guarantees for any individual a whole range of basic freedoms, of which education is one. Article 26 of the declaration states that everyone has a right to education which should be free, at least at elementary and primary stages; elementary education shall be compulsory while technical and professional education shall be made generally available; higher education shall equally be made accessible to all on the basis of merit and parents have the prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children.

Cameroon is one of the 188 UNESCO member states that work in partnership with UNESCO to foster the aims of the UN on education that has as its mission to promote education as a fundamental right. In line with these strategies initiated by UNESCO, Cameroon participated and contributed to the UNESCO sponsored conference of African leaders on the development of education on the African continent at Addis Ababa in 1961 and Tananarive in 1962. Here the Cameroon government, like other African governments, took full commitment to ensure the implementation of the policy of Universal Primary Education (UPE) in Cameroon by the year 1980 (Mbua, 2002).

All of these legal instruments and international initiatives point to the fact that the provision of quality education in every country is a collective responsibility and teacher quality is very essential. Educational reforms, to be successful, will among other things, require fundamental changes of instructional processes and the cultures of teaching. It entails greater collaboration and cooperation between teachers as well as other members of the educational community to lead to these outcomes. "Teaching is one of the most difficult concepts to define in educational studies" (Tambo, 2003). This statement has been confirmed by Orji (1986), who begins by answering the question, "What is teaching?" by saying that, "This may be a difficult question to answer since the lecturer in the University, the tutor in the secondary school, the instructor in the workshop, and of course, the traditional classroom teacher in the primary school all claim to be teaching."

The normative concept of teaching is seen as a generic term (Smith, 1987) that, under certain conditions, it may comprise certain kinds of activities and excludes others. Here, activities included in the

concept of teaching would include training, instruction, indoctrination and conditioning. The activities excluded would be propaganda and intimidation. By this definition or concept, it is imperative that geography teachers should undergo training. Teaching concept that emphasizes the outcome or result of teaching links teaching to learning. They often see learning as a result of teaching. Smith (1960) said that teaching is a "system of actions intended to induce learning." In the same vein, Robertson (1987) pointed out that, "Teaching means action undertaken by one person with the intention of bringing about learning in another."

As Gagne (1978) puts it thus, "by teaching I mean an activity on the part of one person intended to facilitate learning on the part of another." In conformity with Smith, Robertson, Gagne and Dewey, (1934) logically stated that "teaching is to learning as selling is to buying." Geography teachers usually emphasize this concept especially as they want to get good results at the G.C.E. The above logical statement and definitions of teaching led Fenstermacher (1986) to argue that, to say that teaching must lead to learning would be like saying that running a race must lead to winning, or that searching must lead to findings. Considering teaching as a metaphor, teaching is sometimes seen in terms of the teacher's perception of the teaching act or the role of the teacher in the teaching-learning process. McNeil and Wiles (1990) as cited by Tambo (2003) identified three perceptions of the teacher, namely:

- i. Teaching as filling an empty vessel, in which the teacher views students as empty vessels that need to be filled with knowledge, skills and attitudes.
- ii. Teaching as gardening, which considers students as plants growing in a garden, with the teacher providing necessary conditions for each plant to grow to become the best?
- iii. Teaching as a transforming act views the students, as rational beings endowed with potentials for learning and knowledge acquisition. The job of the teacher is to transform this potential knowledge into active and conscious knowledge by way of dialogue or the deductive- inductive process Socratic or Discovery method concept as cited by (Tambo, 2003).

Statement of the Problem

A combination of factors tends to determine the outcome of the teaching and learning process of any discipline. Emmer and Stough (2001) observed that the ability of teachers to organize classrooms and manage the behaviour of their students is critical to achieving positive educational outcomes. Achieving positive educational outcome is often the goal of every teaching/teacher across every discipline and environment. It is equally established that all professions have challenges; teaching/teachers have challenges too. However, there seem to be peculiarities with the teaching/teachers of Geography as accentuated in the General Certificate of Education (G.C.E.) results. Perhaps challenges faced by teachers during the teaching process among others might have culminated in the relatively low performance and even the continuous drop in students' performance in Geography at the G.C.E. examination organized by the Cameroon G.C.E Board. For instance, the results of the G.C.E 'O' Level from 2005-2015 indicates that the highest performance was recorded in 2009 with 71.57% which is considered a good performance by the researcher. From 2010, the results started declining. Looking at the cumulative average for the past 10years (48.39), it is below average. (See appendix A). It is against this backdrop that the researcher sought to examine the challenges teachers face in the teaching of Geography and their impact on the academic performance of students. Furthermore, to propose solutions in resolving these challenges in Meme Division of the South West Region in particular and Cameroon in general.

Objectives of the Study

- Examine whether the challenges faced by teachers in relation to teaching aids have an impact on students' academic performance.
- Determine whether the problems faced by teachers in terms of classroom management strategies have an impact on students' academic performance.
- Investigate whether the difficulties faced by teachers in relation to teachers/students/administrator relationship has an impact on students' academic performance.
- Find out whether the challenges faced by teachers in terms of Geography syllabus have an impact on students' academic performance.

- Determine whether the problems faced by teachers in relation to their working conditions have an impact on students' academic performance
- Propose solutions to the challenges faced by Geography teachers that can be adopted to improve on students' performance

Research Questions

- How do the challenges faced by teachers in relation to teaching aids impact on students' academic performance?
- How do the problems faced by teachers in terms of classroom management strategies impact on students' academic performance?
- How do the difficulties faced by teachers in relation to teachers/students/administrator relationship impact on students' academic performance?
- How do the challenges faced by teachers in terms of Geography syllabus impact on students' academic performance?
- How do the problems faced by teachers in relation to their working conditions impact on students' academic performance?

Review Of Related Literature

Challenges faced by teachers in relation to teaching aids

According to Ojeifo & Ehisuoria (2014), different teaching aids are used in the teaching and learning of geography in Secondary schools. Some of them are maps, thermometers, stereoscopes, sun dial, pictures, aerial photographs, charts, models, radio, television, projectors, and anemometers. These teaching aids are also referred to as instructional materials. Instructional materials are important tools and techniques in the geography teaching-learning process. It provides information to students and also creates in them interest regarding geography. While teaching each topic in geography, instructional materials should be utilized and it should be specified by the concern teacher (Ojeifo and Ehisuoria, 2014). Instructional materials include world globe, topographical maps, atlas, regalia, models, charts, photographs, pictures, etc. These are teaching - learning materials which enhance the knowledge, interest of student and also helps to enhance the quality of teacher's presentation. Instructional materials means, "educational resources used to

improve students' knowledge, abilities, and skills, to monitor their assimilation of information, and to contribute to their overall development and upbringing".

Types of Instructional Materials to be used in the Teaching of Geography:

The following media can be selected for utilization in the teaching of geography based on the criteria afore-discussed.

a. World Globe: This is one of the essential instructional media that a geography teacher should always make reference during his/her teaching. It can be used to teach topics such as the earth's spherical shape, latitude, and longitude, global land and water distribution, world continents, locations of places on the globe, rotation and revolution of the earth among others. It is however disheartening that geography teachers in most schools do not use this medium (world globe) because it is not available in the school or the teachers grossly underutilized it when it is available.

b. Maps: Maps are the important tools used while teaching geography by the teacher. These are "sine qua non" tools for the geographers. Maps are not only important to the teacher but also to the learner. They are of different types like atlas, topographical maps, aerial photographs, etc. The geography teacher is to select the one that is most appropriate and suitable for topic or content to be taught. For instance, for map reading and interpretation, topographical maps will be more appropriate, though other maps can still be consulted as supplements or compliments. For locations of places on the maps, atlas can be conveniently used. However, all these depend on the availability of these various types of maps in the school. The features shown on topographic maps may be divided into three groups:

- relief, which includes hills, valleys, mountains, etc.;
- water features, including lakes, ponds and streams; and
- Cultural features, man-made features like bridges, canals, buildings and roads.

b. Models: These are three-dimensional media that shows the length, breadth and height of the objects. They are very useful in the

teaching of geography if physical or relief features can be put into models. With the use of models, the lesson becomes real, practical and exciting because the learners can visualize, feel and observe in real life how these features exist.

c. Charts, Diagrams and Pictures: Graphical text forms such as diagrams, photographs, drawings, sketches, graphs, schedules, maps, charts, tables and timelines are intended to communicate information in a concise format and illustrate how one piece of information is related to another. Providing students with an approach to reading graphical text helps them to become effective readers. These are two-dimensional media that represent a complete description of phenomenon or place. They can be used complementarily. Therefore, where pictures cannot show all the area or information required, charts and diagrams can be used. They are of different types; single page chart, and flip chart sometimes of multiple pages that are sequentially arranged in order of content or events to be taught. However, in using these media, certain factors should be considered by the teacher such as, the clarity, attractiveness, legibility, boldness, simplicity, balancing and the conspicuousness in the displaying of the media in the classroom situation.

d. Real Objects: The geography teacher can use mineral resources samples like rocks sample, soil samples, etc. as real objects to teach in the classroom. For instance, in teaching a topic like "Types of Rocks", samples of different rocks such as granite, limestone and marbles can be shown to the learners as examples of igneous, sedimentary and metamorphic rocks respectively. This makes learning more concrete, realistic and practical; the learning becomes more permanent in the learners.

e. Meteorological Instruments: These are common weather instruments that the geographers use to measure certain climatic conditions such as rainfall, sunshine, wind direction, air pressure, etc. Some examples of these instruments are; rain gauge, thermometer, wind vane, anemometer, barometer and hygrometer.

f. Projected Media: These are media that use source of power for generating them. They include, overhead projector (OHP), slide projector, opaque projector and the most recent is the computer power point. In fact, these media can be used advisably to teach large class for their cost-effectiveness. Audio-visual media plays an important role in the teaching of geography at higher secondary level. Now many schools have qualified personnel in charge of the audio-visual materials while teaching geography. The University has invested heavily in modernizing classrooms and lecture halls to take advantage of instructional technology, including LCD projectors. LCD's used with a computer project an image onto a screen or blank wall and provides more instructional flexibility in the types of content that can be used in a classroom. Classroom Support will train instructors on how to use the LCD Projectors as well as other classroom technology.

g. Chalkboard: This may be movable, fixed or portable. The fixed or removable chalkboard is usually found in a typical classroom; while the teacher usually produces the portable chalkboard which he can move around. However, chalkboard of any type is mostly used for illustration, clarity of points or concepts and to summarize the content taught. In fact, the geography teachers should mostly use the portable chalkboard for prior preparation and presentation of drawings, diagrams, maps, graphs, etc.; this will save time and energy during classroom presentation. A teacher, instructor or trainer so wishes, can use chalkboard for such straightforward expository purposes as:

- The systematic display of virtually the entire subject matter of a lecture or taught lesson to a class.
- The display of a 'skeleton guide' to such a lecture or lesson, e.g. in the form of a set of section and sub-section headings.
- The display of specific items (maps, diagrams, tables, etc.) during such a lecture or lesson.

h. Printed Media: Printed media includes textbooks, magazines, periodical and reports. Paper cuttings can be consulted or utilized by both teacher and learners in the teaching of geography.

An instructional material in the geography teaching process really plays an important role. Therefore inadequate teaching aids will hinder student understanding of the subject, limit information to students, reduce the quality of the student and their interest in the subject, increase teacher's time for presentation, prevents learning from being practical, exciting and lively. Effective teaching of Geography is possible through the use of instructional materials. Maps, globe, charts, models, meteorological instruments, should be used by the teacher while teaching geography to facilitate and make teaching-learning more effective and more interesting in the classroom.

Importance of instructional resources in Geography teaching and learning

Instructional resources which are educational inputs are of vital importance to the teaching of any subject in the school curriculum. The use of instructional resources would make discovered facts stick firmly to the memory of students (Savoury, 1958). He added that a well-planned and imaginative use of visual aids in lessons would do much to banish apathy, supplement inadequacy of books as well as arouse students' interest by giving them something practical to see and do, and at the same time helping to train them to think for themselves. He further suggested that a catalogue of useful visual aids is good for teaching geography i.e. pictures, post cards, diagrams, filmstrips and models. Boardman (1985) said that there are substantial numbers of classes in Kenya where no use is made of atlases, maps or globes which are basic to the effective teaching. He further asserted that in the majority of classes, essential skills and ideas are rarely given sufficient attention. He added that research has shown that classes where teachers employ minimal resources in their teaching register low performance. Fitzpatrick (1993) asserted that multi-media in particular is appropriate for Geography education since its concept is learned through text, maps, pictures and sound to achieve the fullest learning experience.

In computer based instructional media, Davidson (1996) stated that the use of such media in geography lesson is imperative as it make a valuable contribution

to the quality of student's learning. Such media can be used in several ways in geography lessons. PowerPoint, for instance can be used to present geographical issues and data boxes for collective weather data electronically. He also found that computer graphic maps are effective ways of presenting spatial information and for geography courses. Such maps are considered the most important for illustrations. Teachers need to use them effectively in the classrooms and give opportunity for students to learn about different types of maps starting from simple maps to most complex geographical information system (GIS) maps. In Geography, a child learns better if the teaching is supported by concrete and objective materials that give the child firsthand knowledge and experience. For example when teaching field work, a trip to the riverside, a visit to a factory, a forest, some specimens of seeds, fruits or vegetables, rocks and minerals would form concrete illustrations in geography lesson. Some difficulties of apprehensions are cleared up with the use of illustration since explanation are simplified and given vividness with the help of illustrations.

Challenges faced by teachers in relation to Classroom management strategies

Classroom management is a cardinal feature of the total education process. It contains all the steps through which interaction between the educator and the learner take place. Classroom management is the process of ensuring that classroom lessons run smoothly despite of disruptive behaviour by students. The term also refers to the prevention of disruptive behaviour of students (Berliner, 1988). Classroom management refers to all those essential activities which are highly necessary not only to create but also to maintain a supportive and orderly atmosphere. It includes planning and preparation of teaching and learning materials, organization of the materials, decoration of the classroom, creation of expectation and establishment and enforcement of rules and routines in the classroom (Tan, Parsons, Hinson and Sardo-Brown, 2003).

Baker (2005) observed that improved teacher training in classroom management is a critical part in improving academic performance in a particular subject. Factors contributing to effective classroom management include: teaching methodology, lesson planning and preparation, interpersonal relationships and student motivation. Paine et al (1983) observed that structuring a classroom so that it supports positive

student behaviour requires prior planning. The structure of the classroom environment should decrease the likelihood of inappropriate student behaviour and increases desirable student interactions and consequently improves academic performance. A classroom environment would enable learners to study in a way that is interesting, enjoyable and purposeful. Among models to restructure a good classroom environment include: use of a variety of teaching methods and involving students to numerous learning activities, physical class arrangement that allows a teacher to access students, efficient use of class time and ensuring that students interact positively during cooperative learning activities (Emmer and Stough, 2001).

Kerr and Nelson (2002) asserted that the use of rules is a "powerful, preventive component of classroom organization and management plans." Rules are aimed at establishing the expected behaviours, what to be reinforced and the consequences for inappropriate behaviour. Thus emphasis of effective class discipline helps to cut down on discipline problems and leave the classroom with fewer interruptions and disruptions.

Wong (2007) believed that student performance is influenced by how well the procedures are laid out and taught to them. To instill class discipline, teachers should introduce class rules early enough when the year is beginning and make sure they are understood by all. The teacher should be fair and impartial across all the students. In case of disruption within a lesson, the teacher should deal with the interruption with as little distraction as possible. Teachers should consider over planning as a recipe to avoid giving students free-time within the lesson. The teacher should be consistent in that they should not afford to ignore negative behaviour.

Collins (2007) advocated for "cooperative discipline" where the teacher and students work together to make decisions. To him teachers should come up with a code of conduct that shows how students should behave and not how they should not behave. This instills discipline in a child as they know what is expected of them. Glenn et al (2003) emphasized the need for teachers to hold class meetings severally. Class meetings encourage respect among teacher and students. Kerr and Nelson (2002) encouraged the use of humor as a way to engage students and activate their learning. To them, when teachers share a laugh

or a smile with students, they help students feel more comfortable and open to learning. Moreover, humor brings enthusiasm, positive feelings, and optimism to the classroom. Teachers are expected to conduct a need analysis to identify the needs of students so as to capture their attention during learning process. Students need to be taught respect for self and others so that they can be able to function healthily in the society (Rogers, 2008).

Theoretical Framework

The Functionalist Theory

The functionalist theory sees society as a complex system whose parts work together to promote solidarity and stability; it states that our social lives are guided by social structure, which are relatively stable patterns of social behaviour (Macdonald, 1997). Social structure is understood in terms of social functions, which are prerequisites for the operations of society. All social structures contribute to the maintenance and growth of a society or system. The major terms and concepts developed by anthropologists and sociologists in this theory include: order, structure, function (manifest or direct functions and latent or hidden, indirect functions), and equilibrium. Those who hold this view ask such questions as: what holds society together? What keeps it steady? The functionalist theory pays considerable attention to the persistence of shared ideas in society. The functional aspect in the structural-functionalist theory stresses the role played by each component part in the social system, whereas the structural perspective suggests an image of society wherein individuals are constrained by the social forces, social backgrounds and by group memberships. Functionalists also argued that society should be understood as a system of interdependent parts. They believed that there are specific requirements (functional prerequisites) that must be met in all social systems and that these can provide the basis for the comparative analysis of social institutions (Holmwood, 2005).

This theory has been challenged by conflict theorists, people who think like Karl Marx. To the critics, its emphasis on stability and order while neglecting conflict and changes which are so vital in any society constitutes a weakness. Functionalism as a theory assumes that education is fair and it rewards the best and ignores social inequalities that may restrict attainment. The Functionalist theory can be used to explain organizational processes and outcomes.

Secondary schools are formal organizations composed of many parts that work together in a division of labour relationship in order to achieve stated objectives contained in various pieces of legislation, notably the law of orientation for basic, secondary and teacher education of April 14, 1998. The Functionalist theory is considered relevant to this study because it emphasizes inter-dependence of parts and processes. A secondary school can be broken down into parts comprising teachers, students, support staff, appointed administrators, and parents, among others. These parts are inter-related and interdependent in such a way that the removal of one part or its inadequate contribution will hurt the system's functioning. Teachers work or are expected to work in ways that complement and strengthen each other. Socialization is widely acknowledged as a strategy to reduce teacher isolation and make the school a welcoming environment for beginning teachers to enable them function in ways that help rather than hurt the school as a whole.

Constructivist Theory

According to Jean Piaget, there are two schools of thought that fall within this theory, social constructivism and cognitive constructivism. Social constructivism emphasizes the collaborative nature of learning. Social constructivism was developed by Soviet psychologist Lev Vygotsky (1978). Vygotsky was a cognitive psychologist who rejected some of the assumptions made by cognitivists such as Piaget. For example, one of the assumptions he disagreed with is the idea that it was possible to separate learning from its social context. He argued that all cognitive functions originate in, and must therefore be explained as products of social interactions and that learning was not simply the assimilation and accommodation of new knowledge by learners but a process by which learners are integrated into a knowledge community (Vygotsky, 1978). Vygotsky emphasized the role of language and culture in cognitive development arguing that they play essential roles both in human intellectual development and in how humans perceive the world around them. Vygotsky distinguished between two developmental levels: The level of **actual** development is that at which the learner is capable of solving problems independently. The level of **potential** development (the "zone of proximal development") is the level of development that the learner is capable of reaching under the guidance of teachers or in collaboration with peers.

The most influential exponent of cognitive constructivism was Swiss child psychologist Jean Piaget. Piaget (1968) rejected the idea that learning was the passive assimilation of given knowledge. Instead, he proposed that learning is a dynamic process comprising successive stages of adaptation to reality during which learners actively construct knowledge by creating and testing their own theories of the world. Piaget's theory has two main strands: first, an account of the mechanisms by which cognitive development takes place; and second, an account of the four main stages of cognitive development through which children pass.

This theory is important to this study because, it is important for new teachers to know that the classroom is no longer a place where the teacher pours knowledge into passive students, who wait like empty vessels to be filled, but to know that students are urged to be actively involved in their own process of learning. In constructivist's classrooms, both teacher and students think of knowledge as a dynamic, ever-changing view of the world we live in and the ability to successfully stretch and explore that view. In addition, constructivism is very relevant to this study because socialization is a process during which neophytes or new teachers learn from their more experienced counterparts. Furthermore, perceptions of the socialization experience will differ from one teacher to another because they are socially constructed. A new teacher's perception of the socialization process constitutes his/her reality with the potential to profoundly shape attitudes and observed behaviours during the teaching and learning process. If learning is a social process, then the challenge is for the various education stakeholders to create environments that enable new teachers to optimize learning from more experienced colleagues.

Experiential Learning Theory

In the mid 1980's, David Kolb proposed that adult learning is more effective (that is, processed at much deeper levels) when learners are more directly involved rather than passively receiving knowledge transmitted by teachers. Kolb asserted that a person learns through his or her discovery and experience. He developed this theory in order to explain the connections between the human developmental stages of maturation, learning processes, and experience. He believed that experience shapes the way learners grasp knowledge, which then affects their cognitive development. Kolb developed what he called the

“experiential learning cycle” with four distinct stages of learning. While the cycle can start at any stage, all stages are required in order for learners to learn effectively. These stages are as follows:

- Concrete experience - this stage is characterized by active learning as opposed to passive receipt of knowledge (that is, learning about something directly by being involved with the material rather than learning about it).
- Reflective observation - this requires learners (in this case new teachers) thinking critically about the learning (socialization) experience.
- Abstract conceptualization - linking the experience to the theory or concepts underlying it.
- Active experimentation - testing out one's learning in new situations.

The experiential learning theory has been challenged by Boud et al (1985), on grounds that it pays insufficient attention to the process of reflection, the claims made for the four different learning styles are extravagant and that the theory takes very little account of different cultural experiences or conditions. Regardless of these criticisms, this theory is relevant to this study because socialization is a process during which neophytes or new teachers learn from their more experienced counterparts through experience. It is also relevant because it helps new teachers to relate theoretical concepts to real-life situations as well as help them create knowledge through the transformation of experience.

Empirical Framework

Studies done in Kenya on the availability and utilization of instructional resources showed that schools have scanty resources whose use is very vital in teaching and learning process. Ogoma (1987), in a survey of resources used for teaching social studies in Nairobi primary schools, found out that resources use by teachers are non-recommended textbooks, charts and realia. He said that most of the resources are bought while others are improvised by both teachers and learners. Audio and visual resources such as cassettes players and projectors were lacking in most schools.

Kimui (1988) revealed that teaching institutions lack many instructional media, in a study of the availability and use of resources in Kenya teachers training colleges. Print media and chalkboard were

used widely. Okoko (1991) observed that there was an acute shortage of textbooks in the teaching and learning of history in secondary schools in south Nyanza. However, she did not look at other instructional media in her study.

Orina (2001) also found out that print media were widely used in teaching Geography. In a survey of the availability, acquisition and utilization of instructional resources in the teaching of Geography in secondary schools of Kisii district, he revealed that the least available resources were, geographical magazines encyclopedia, posters, models, cameras, and television sets. The available resources were found inadequate. However, most of the resources available in school were accessible to the teachers. Some textbooks, encyclopedia and audio visual such as films and film projectors, video, tape recorder, television sets, radio, camera and radio cassettes were inaccessible to the students in some schools.

According to Oladejo et. al. (2011), who carried out a study on “Instructional Materials and Students’ Academic Achievement in Physics,” examined the effect of using standardized and improvised instructional materials on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Physics Students in Oyo State, Nigeria. The research design adopted was quasi-experimental of the pretest, post-test non-randomized control group. Purposive sampling was used to obtain a sample of three co-educational secondary schools. Each school provided one class for the study. Two instruments were used in the study, the Physics Achievement Test (PAT) to measure students’ achievement and Teachers Instructional Guide (TIG) to train the teachers in the experimental groups. The instrument was pilot tested to ascertain reliability. The reliability coefficient was 0.76. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Data were analysed using ANOVA and ANCOVA.

Findings revealed that there is a significant difference in the achievement of students taught using standard instructional materials, those taught with improvised instructional material and those in the conventional instruction. Thus, the students taught with improvised instructional materials obtained the highest achievement score at post-test ($F=74.94$), followed by those with standard instructional materials ($F=63.07$), while the control group scored the lowest ($F=39.89$). Also, there was no significant effect of gender on

students’ achievement in Physics although, females did better than males.

Finally, there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on student achievement in Physics. Thus, Physics teachers need to be resourceful in instructional materials selection, planning and utilization so as to reduce the cost of production and maintenance of instructional materials. The researchers concluded that the utilization of improvised instructional materials promote and enhance effective teaching-learning process, thus, Physics teachers should be encouraged to use them in secondary education programme.

Research Methodology

Research Design

There are many types of research designs but that employed for this study was the survey design. Survey research involves the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions (Amin, 2005). The survey was considered the most appropriate for this study because it is an efficient method for systematically collecting data from a broad spectrum of individuals and in educational setting. In addition, survey design owes its continued popularity to its versatility (flexibility), and generalizability. The researcher used questionnaires designed for teachers and students to gather information on the difficulties faced by teachers in the teaching of Geography and their solutions. Interview was conducted with Principals of schools to appraise the difficulties teachers face in the teaching of Geography. Therefore both quantitative and qualitative approaches of this design were used. The vision behind quantitative approach is to weigh or quantify indicators to guide or aid decision-making or for comparative reasons while in qualitative approach, one is more concerned with the concept and not the weight. This is because a concept or idea can emanate from one or very few respondents but can still be very significant in providing an in-depth information or understanding of the subject matter. However, it is generally recommended that qualitative and quantitative approaches should be bridged following the positivism principle. This is a principle whereby concepts or ideas that emanates from thematic and or content analysis are grounded as to appreciate the level of emphasis while remaining in the qualitative perspective in the interpretation and presentation of findings (Nana, 2012).

Sample of the Population

A sample is a smaller group of subjects which represents a larger population (Amin, 2005). It is also called the subset of a population. The accessible population for this study was distributed as follows: 79 teachers were sampled from 27 schools (i.e. the 12

selected schools and 15 others so as to have a proportionate population for teachers), 120 students and 12 principals from 12 selected schools (4 Public, 4 Confessional and 4 Lay Private), bringing the total to a sample of 211.

Table 1: Sample Distribution of Teachers, Principals and Students in Accessible Schools

Schools	No. of Teachers	No. of Principals	No. of Students
CCAS Kumba	4	1	10
GHS Kake	4	1	10
GHS Kumba-Mbeng	5	1	10
GBHS Kumba	4	1	10
GHS Kamlikum	5	1	10
BHS Kumba	2	1	10
St John College	3	1	10
FUGOSEC Kumba	1	1	10
Divine High School Kumba	2	1	10
Victory Comp. College Kumba	2	1	10
GLOBICOL Kumba	2	1	10
KUCAS Kumba	1	1	10
Martin Luther King Academic	3		
St. Francis College	4		
All Saints Secondary School	4		
BAAS Kumba	3		
AGES Kumba	1		
CCCHS	3		
PCSS KUMBA	4		
Union Comprehensive College Kwakwa	2		
Diligent Bilingual College	2		
GSS Kang Barombi	3		
GHS Bombe	3		
GHS Malende	3		
ETA college	2		
Kumba City College	2		
GBHS Kossala	5		
TOTAL	79	12	120

Table 2: Summary of findings

Research questions	Test statistics	Comments
How do the challenges faced by teachers in relation to teaching aids impact on students' academic performance in Geography?	Pearson correlation test	There was statistically enough evidence that the use of teaching aids improved students' performance in geography ($r=0.327$; $P=0.032$).
How do the problems faced by teachers in terms of classroom management strategies impact on students' academic performance in Geography?	Pearson correlation test	Classroom management was perceived as having no effect on the academic performance in geography given that the correlation coefficient was closer to 0 ($r=0.05$, $P=0.884$).
How do the difficulties faced by teachers in relation to teachers/students relationship impact on students' academic performance in Geography?	Pearson correlation test	Teacher-student relationship had a positive effect on academic performance in geography though this effect was not significant ($r=0.107$; $P=0.244$).
How do the difficulties faced by teachers in relation to teachers/administrator relationship impact on students' academic performance in Geography?	Pearson correlation test	Teacher-administrator relationship had a positive though not significant effect on students' academic performance in geography ($r=0.107$; $P=0.755$).
How do the challenges faced by teachers in terms of Geography syllabus have an impact on students' academic performance in Geography?	Pearson correlation test	There was a significant positive effect of the implementation of syllabus on students' academic performance in geography ($r=0.229$; $P=0.012$).
How do the problems faced by teachers in relation to their working conditions impact on students' academic performance in Geography?	Pearson correlation test	The findings showed that teachers' working condition had no effect on students' performance in geography ($r=0.052$, $P=0.879$).

Discussions And Educational Implications Of The Study

This finding ties to that of Orina (2001) who found out that the availability, acquisition and use of instructional media besides print in teaching Geography were limited. In a survey of the availability, acquisition and utilization of instructional resources in the teaching of Geography in secondary schools of Kisii district, he revealed that the least available resources were, geographical magazines, encyclopedia, posters, models, cameras, and

television sets. The available resources were found inadequate. However, most of the resources available in school were accessible to the teachers. Some textbooks, encyclopedia and audio visual such as films and film projectors, video, tape recorder, television sets, radio, camera and radio cassettes were inaccessible to the students in some schools.

In computer based instructional media, Davidson (1996), stated that the use of such media in geography lesson is imperative as it make a valuable contribution to the quality of student's learning. Such media can be

used in several ways in geography lessons. PowerPoint, for instance can be used to present geographical issues and data logs for collective weather data electronically. He also found that computer graphic maps were effective ways of presenting spatial information and for geography lessons, such maps are considered the most important for illustrations. Teachers need to use them effectively in the classrooms and give opportunity to students to learn about different types of maps starting from simple maps to most complex geographical information system (GIS) maps.

In Geography, a child learns better if the teaching is supported by concrete and objective materials that give the child firsthand knowledge and experience. For example when teaching field work, a trip to the riverside, a visit to a factory, a forest, some specimens of seeds, fruits or vegetables, rocks and minerals would form concrete illustrations in geography lesson. Some difficulties of apprehensions are cleared up with the use of illustration since explanation are simplified and given vividness with the help of illustrations.

However, Luz (2015) pointed out that by having a good relationship with students, teachers can offer to students chances to be motivated and feel engaged in the learning process. Students will be engaged actively in the learning instead of being passive learners. He investigated how the use of communicative approach and cooperative learning strategies while teaching do affect and improve students' learning performance. The results showed that teachers and students value a supportive and caring relationship between them and that interaction is essential to the teacher-student relationship. This sense of caring and supporting from teachers motivates students to become more interested learners. Students benefit and are motivated when their teachers create a safe and trustful environment. Also the methods and strategies teachers used make students feel engaged and stimulated to participate in the learning process. The students have in their mind that a positive relationship with their teachers positively impacts their interest and motivation in school which contributes to the enhancement of the learning process.

The idea here was to find out whether the challenges faced by teachers in terms of Geography syllabus have an impact on students' academic performance in Geography. Students in their greater percentage were

satisfied with the implementation of the syllabus though 89.2% of them agreed that it was broad. Students' perception of implementation of syllabus was only dependent on performance ($P < 0.05$) whereby those who performed well were the most satisfied with proportion of 72.4%. There was a significant positive effect on the implementation of syllabus on students' academic performance in geography ($r = 0.229$; $P = 0.012$).

The results of this finding agreed with the work of Musasia, Nakhanu & Wekesa (2012) who carried out a study on the "Investigation of Factors that Influence Syllabus Coverage in Secondary School Geography in Kenya" The main objective was to determine the percentage of the syllabus covered, and correlate it with student performance. 16 out of 85 schools were purposively selected and used in the study. The head teacher, the head of Geography department, and two randomly selected Geography teachers from each of the 16 schools took part in the study. In total there were 64 respondents. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study, and data collected using three questionnaires. Correlation between syllabus coverage and student performance using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was 0.8343. Furthermore, a One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was determined and confirmed that syllabus coverage has a significant effect on student performance in Geography. Furthermore, a number of factors were identified as being responsible for early, late or non-coverage of the syllabus.

This result is in contrary with the study carried out by The Condition of Education (1996), which stated that to deliver high quality education, schools must attract, develop, and retain effective teachers. Working conditions play an important role in a school's ability to do so. Schools that are able to offer their teachers a safe, pleasant, and supportive working environment and adequate compensation are better able to attract and retain good teachers and motivate them to do their best. Teachers' working conditions are important to students as well as teachers because they affect how much individual attention teachers can give to students.

Large class sizes or disruptive students, for example, can make both teaching and learning difficult. Some aspects of teachers' working conditions go along with the job regardless of where a teacher works. For example, teacher salaries tend to be low relative to those earned by similarly qualified individuals in

other professions regardless of the type or location of the school. Other aspects of teachers' working conditions, such as school safety, vary widely from school to school. Thus, in addition to being concerned about teachers' working conditions in general, we need to pay attention to the types of schools that tend to have desirable or difficult working conditions and, for equity reasons, to the characteristics of the students who attend them. A number of aspects of teachers' working conditions include; workload, compensation, school and government support for teachers' professional development, school decision making, school safety, student readiness to learn and public respect for teachers.

Recommendations

The results obtained from data analysis do attest that there is much to be said about the challenges teachers face in teaching Geography in relation to teaching aids, classroom management strategies, teachers/students/administrator relationship, syllabus and working conditions and their impact on students' academic performance in Geography. The solutions to these challenges faced by teachers cannot be realized by the teachers alone. Therefore the researcher's recommendations were formulated in the form of appeal to curriculum planners (policy makers), proprietors of schools, teachers, students and parents.

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that government could regularly organize seminars, workshops and training programs to foster teacher's mastering of the subject matter and other effective factors that can advance students learning. Government could also make sure that teachers employed possessed the necessary teaching qualifications to certify them to teach Geography. Different teachers could be made to handle different aspects of Geography. This would enable them to be more efficient as they would be made to handle what they have interest in and capable of doing.

In addition, they could provide needed and required facilities and materials for teaching and learning. Since the schools do not have adequate geography aids, it is only responsible that the government through the ministry of education carry out a comprehensive teaching aids need assessment for all the schools with a view to determining what is required to be provided in terms of type, quantity and quality. After this assessment, modalities could be put in place to meet these needs in the shortest possible time. The modalities must also incorporate

replacement procedure so that obsolete ones can regularly be replaced. By so doing geography aids will not be in short supply and current aids will be in use.

Lastly, policy makers could revise the Geography syllabus since both teachers and student complained of it broad nature. From the findings of this study, majority of teachers and students testified that the syllabus is usually incomplete before the writing of official examinations. Some teachers tend to rush with the lessons in order to complete the syllabus thus leaving the students empty leading to poor performance.

The proprietors of private and mission schools should lay emphasis on the Geography teachers they employ in terms of qualification/training and year of experience in the teaching field. They should insist on pedagogy either before recruitment or after by calling in experts from time to time to close up inadequacy through in-service training, seminars and workshop to prepare their teachers aptly enough to handle individual subjects effectively and efficiently.

This study has shown that improvisation of geography teaching aids by teachers in the schools was poor due to lack of finance by the teachers and poor fabrication. To overcome the problem of finance, it is recommended that each school should have improvisation fund from which teachers can apply for the purpose of improvisation. Contribution to this fund should come from school levies, parent-teachers association and old student Associations.

Teachers could constantly make provision for professional development. Teachers themselves (with the help of the Teachers Council, teacher unions and professional Associations) need to be much more consciously aware of and able to articulate what they know about pedagogy and work towards developing an increased sense of self-esteem about special pedagogical and professional knowledge required for effective teaching. This will lead to a positive impact on the performance of the students they teach.

Students should develop the concept of self-efficacy, the belief that one can master a situation and produce positive outcomes. Bandura (1994, 1997, 1998, 2000) believed that self-efficacy is a critical factor in whether or not students achieve. Students should also maximize their academic learning time as emphasized by Fisher, et al (1980).

Parents should endeavor to meet regularly with teachers to discuss problems faced by their children in schools with a view to finding solutions to these problems. Parents being at the pivot of the education of their children, there should be a collaborative effort between schools and parents to curb the problems of poor performances in class examination and national examinations. Parents should find out from teachers why their children are not performing well and teachers should always endeavor to find out from parents the possible problems that the children are facing at home. If parents, teachers and students do not work collaboratively to curb the problem, the situation will not improve, leading to poor performance of students. Therefore, the researcher strongly recommends the joint collaborative effort between the teacher, parents, students and school administrators to help curb the poor performance of students.

Conclusion

Geography as a secondary school subject enables students to explore and understand the relationship between the earth and its people through the study of space, place and environment. These three elements (or macro-concepts) form the core of Geography in secondary education. However, there are problems and difficulties faced in learning Geography (Nazli, 2009). The main problems are; instructors are not sufficient in geography education; the removal of some geography courses in the syllabus negatively affects geography education; and that teacher trainees in the field have low motivation. When planning for teaching and learning in the area of geography, a variety of teaching strategies need to be considered (Standish, 2009). When the teacher is designing, planning, and structuring geography lessons, potential areas of difficulty may emerge for these students as they engage with classroom experiences and methodologies while learning Geography. Therefore, there is a need to use some resources to facilitate the teaching and learning of Geography.

The study findings indicated that teachers face challenges in relation to teaching aid. Majority of teachers were not satisfied with the availability and the nature of teaching aids in Geography mean while there was statistically enough evidence that the use of teaching aids improved students' performance in geography. Thus, the limited use of specific and appropriate instructional resources is a factor that poses a challenge to teaching and learning of

Geography. Therefore the teaching and learning of Geography is affected by the availability of instructional materials in the schools. Instructional resources are important inputs for effective teaching and learning. As noted in the study, most schools were inadequately in possession of these instructional materials in aiding the teaching and learning of geography. Finally, the broad nature of Geography syllabus with limited time and inadequate teachers has affected its coverage before student seat for their end of year examinations. There was a significant positive effect on the implementation of syllabus on students' academic performance in geography.

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